

Repositioning Public Libraries to meet the Information Needs of Farmers in Nigeria: a case of Dass Local Government, Bauchi State

Idris Ibrahim Saleh (Ph.D)¹

Ismaila Aliyu (Ph.D)²

¹*Department of Library and Information Science, Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto*

²*Department of Geography, Usmanu Danfodiyo University, Sokoto*

idris.ibrahim1@udusok.edu.ng; ismaila.aliyu@udusok.edu.ng

Abstract

This study examined the repositioning of public libraries to effectively meet the information needs of farmers in Nigeria, using Dass Local Government Area of Bauchi State as a case study. A descriptive research design was adopted, and a purposive sampling technique was used to select eighty-eight (88) farmers. Data were collected through a structured questionnaire and analyzed using descriptive statistics. The findings revealed that although farmers have significant information needs in areas such as agricultural practices, economic activities, education, politics, and environmental issues, the use of public libraries as a source of information remains low. Instead, most farmers rely on informal sources such as family, friends, and fellow farmers. The study further identified major challenges hindering effective use of public libraries, including language barriers, low awareness of library services, long distance to library facilities, inadequate relevant materials, insufficient personnel, and limited access time. The study concludes that public libraries in the study area have not been adequately repositioned to meet the information needs of farmers. It therefore recommends increased funding, improved library resources, staff training and retraining, development of localized and translated information materials, and enhanced outreach and awareness programmes to promote effective utilization of public library services among farmers.

Keywords: Public libraries, information needs, farmers, library services, Nigeria.

Introduction

United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO) (1994) define Library as, an organized collection of printed books, periodical and graphic or audio-visual materials with a trained staff to provide and facilitate the use of such materials as required to meet the informational research, educational and recreational needs of users. This is because different types of libraries played different functions aimed at satisfying their various users with abundant resources. To this end, whether print or non-print resources, disseminating these materials could be through paper format such as books, encyclopedias, newspapers, etc, or non-print format such as microforms, flash drives, computers etc, as they can be accessible off and online for the purpose of adding to knowledge and decision making.

Public libraries thrive in most nations of the world and are often considered an essential part of an educated and literate population who strive to enhance their ways of life. International Federation of Library Association and Institutions (IFLA)/UNESCO on Public Library Manifesto writes; this Manifesto proclaims UNESCO's belief in the public library as a living force for education, culture and information, and as an essential agent for the fostering of peace and spiritual welfare through the minds of men and women". Public libraries are libraries established for the general public and they are supervised, financed and supported by the state or local government of a country. Public libraries are set up by state law supported from the general public funds and administered for the advantage of the citizens of the town, city, or region which maintains it on the basis of equal access to all, whether they are artisans, businessmen and women or professionals. It does not differentiate as its doors are open to all categories of people. The American library association (2017) considered that the public library should provide printed and audio-visual materials to meet the individual and group needs of its community for information, self-realization, recreation and cultural growth among others.

Public libraries in rural Africa have increasingly become focal points for knowledge dissemination and capacity building (Bhanu & Dhanyasree, 2025; Dent et al., 2014; Mojapelo, 2018). These libraries, often supported by local governments, non-governmental organizations (NGOs), and international development agencies, have the potential to bridge the information gap between traditional practices and modern farming techniques. Public and community libraries play an important role in providing farmers with access to basic agricultural information essential for improved productivity and sustainable livelihoods. By serving as local information hubs, libraries disseminate knowledge on crop production, soil and water management, pest and disease control, climate variability, and market prices through print, audiovisual, and digital resources (Aguolu, 2020). In rural areas, libraries complement agricultural extension services by offering continuous and reliable access to information, thereby supporting informed decision-making among farmers. Through information literacy support and community outreach, libraries help bridge the gap between research institutions and farming communities, contributing to agricultural development and food security (Aina, 2006; Dent, 2012; Mojapelo, 2018; Sobalaje et al., 2023).

Tarvinder (2014) described a public library as essentially a free library sponsored by public funds, providing nonpartisan service to all the members of a local community despite its cast and creed and a democratic institution providing information, education and culture to each users according to needs. That is why Umoh, Habib and Yusuf (2018) reported that public library is an information agency that assists its patrons in their choice of reading information resources. The library gives the community the opportunity to acquire learning experiences at little or no cost. It also connects the immediate community to the outside world as regards acquisition of knowledge. It improves the educational development programs of the society by fulfilling continuous education programs. Therefore public libraries have aided in developing society and its citizens by facilitating implementation of learning programs to users like farmers and market women which equip them with the basic skills to enable them succeed in a changing society (Umoh, Habib & Yusuf, 2018).

Regarding their information needs, rural farmers would want to get information on where, when and how to get fertilizers, pesticides, seeds and mechanical equipment; on the prices of products and names of suppliers; on credit facilities from the government or banks for loans to small-scale industries and the legal implications surrounding such loans; and on current prices and market

situations etc. Since the success of rural development programs rests on the availability and use of special information for proper planning and implementation, it becomes imperative to identify the areas of need of the rural farmers and to provide the information needed. According to Harande (2019), the greatest area of information needs by rural Nigerians is in agriculture; these include planting treated seeds, soil conservation, prevention of plants and animal diseases, fertilizer application, farm machineries, recommended thinning practices, proper storage of farm products, marketing techniques, cooperative activities and other agro-cultural activities.

Meeting the information needs of farmers has been a major bottleneck of public libraries especially in the developing countries. Idiegbeyan-Ose et al (2018) opined that despite the benefits rendered by public library, the provision of information to farmers has become a setback to some extent. The public library is positioned to promote access to information which will translate to development of the society; however, this organisation is faced with a lot of challenges in reaching its objectives. A major problem facing public libraries is inadequate finance, irrelevant resources, inadequate manpower, and most libraries in rural areas in Nigeria are still extension of urban public libraries instituted by state governments. Most of their activities are directed by the urban public library's librarian who is not familiar with the complexity of the information needs of the rural farmers.

However, repositioning public libraries to meet the information needs of farmers requires shifting from a passive, book-centric model to an active, outreach-based, and technology-driven approach. Major strategies involve providing localized agricultural content, utilizing mobile technology, and partnering with agricultural stakeholders to deliver timely, actionable information to rural communities. According to Mole (2024), the strategies include:

Public libraries can be effectively repositioned to meet the information needs of farmers through several strategic approaches. These include information repackaging and localization, where complex agricultural information is simplified into accessible formats such as pamphlets, posters, and summaries in local dialects, covering areas like pesticide use, soil management, and weather forecasts. In addition, mobile library and outreach services should be implemented to bridge the gap between rural farmers and library facilities by bringing information resources, including books and digital tools, directly to farming communities. The integration of information and communication technologies (ICTs) is also essential, as libraries can provide free internet access and training on the use of modern tools such as smartphones, WhatsApp, and agricultural websites to enhance farmers' access to market and technical information.

Furthermore, collaborative partnerships with agricultural research institutes, extension agents, and community centers can facilitate the organization of workshops, seminars, and other knowledge-sharing programmes. Establishing specialized agricultural information centers within rural libraries, equipped with relevant print and non-print materials, can also serve as vital information hubs. Given the high level of illiteracy among rural farmers, the use of oral information techniques—where librarians interpret and communicate information verbally—should be encouraged. Finally, regular assessment of farmers' information needs through surveys and direct engagement is necessary to ensure that library services remain relevant and responsive to areas such as credit facilities, land management, and marketing.

Among the challenges encountered by rural libraries is the inadequacy of material in local languages. Most of the resources (books, non-books) are published in English language when, in actual fact, most of the rural populace have deficiency in reading and writing (Momodu, 2002). Issues of inadequate finance, training and retraining of staff; illiteracy rate of the citizens' is high, plus outdated and irrelevant collections of the public libraries as well as lack of recognition on the part of government to know the importance of libraries to economic, social, educational and national development of the country is often being the problems. Some scholars, (Umoh et al., 2018: Emmanuel, 2022: Jimma, 2018) studied public library's roles on rural communities' development, and bemoaned little or no study on repositioning public libraries to meet the actual information needs of rural farmers in Dass Local Government, Bauchi State, Nigeria. Therefore, this study examined the repositioning public library to meet the information needs of rural farmers in Dass Local Government, Bauchi State, Nigeria.

Objectives of the Study

The main objective of this study is to examine the repositioning of public library to meet the information needs of farmers in Dass, Bauchi State, Nigeria. The specific objectives were:

1. repositioning public library to ascertain the information needs of farmers in Dass Local Government, Bauchi state;
2. repositioning public library to determine sources of information used by farmers in Dass Local government, Bauchi state; and
3. repositioning public library to identify the challenges encountered by Bauchi State Public Library towards the provision of information to farmers in Dass Local Government, Bauchi state.

Literature Review

The term information refers to facts provided or learned about something or someone (Merriam-Webster Dictionary, 2019). Idris (2017) defines information need as the desire of an individual or group to locate and obtain information to satisfy a conscious or unconscious need, noting that information can be regarded as a vital resource that facilitates human existence. Akeweta, Tata, and Nandi (2018) examined the information needs of farmers in Song Local Government Area of Adamawa State, Nigeria. Their findings revealed that all respondents required information on how, where, and when to access agricultural inputs such as improved seeds, fertilizers, herbicides, and insecticides. Additionally, 62% of the respondents indicated a need for information on transportation systems and daily market price trends to enable them to determine the appropriate time to sell their farm produce for maximum profit.

In another study, John, Wakilu, and Olateju (2018) investigated the extent of agricultural information needs among farmers in Lagos State. The study revealed that farmers showed limited interest in information related to irrigation and government schemes on agricultural weeding and thinning. However, a significant proportion of respondents expressed a strong need for information

on pest and disease management, weather conditions, soil and water conservation, crop storage, and market information. Similarly, Emmanuel (2022) examined the information needs and information-seeking behavior of rural farmers in Okpokwu Local Government Area of Benue State. The findings indicated that farmers' information needs span multiple areas, including improved seed varieties, agrochemicals, integrated pest and disease management systems, loan and credit facilities, marketing strategies, export opportunities, organic farming, climate change, resource utilization, and sustainable agriculture. Other identified needs include value addition, post-harvest processing, education, access to roads, storage and preservation facilities, processing machinery, soil fertility testing equipment, animal breeds, feeds, animal health, and fattening practices.

Despite these needs, public libraries in Nigeria face several challenges in meeting the information demands of farmers. Idiegbeyan-Ose et al. (2018) identified key issues such as inadequate information repackaging, the attitudes of farmers and extension agents, poor infrastructure, low levels of competency, and the educational background of farmers. Similarly, Salman, Mugwisi, and Mostert (2017) explored factors limiting access to and use of public library services in both urban and rural areas of Nigeria. Their findings highlighted challenges such as irregular electricity supply, disorganized and outdated library materials, insufficient copies of information resources, non-functional catalogues, inadequate facilities, negative staff attitudes, and a shortage of professionally qualified librarians. Additional challenges include the absence of e-library facilities and poor working environments.

Furthermore, Tinuoye, Omeluzor, and Emeka-Ukwu (2019) investigated the revitalization of public library services in Delta State for national development. The study revealed that 63% of respondents were dissatisfied with the role of public libraries in providing access to information materials, largely due to inadequate funding. In addition, 69% of respondents agreed that insufficient funding significantly hinders the effective operation of public libraries. The findings also indicated that inadequate infrastructure—such as poor buildings, lack of air conditioning, insufficient seating, unconducive environments, limited internet access, poor lighting, and lack of basic facilities—negatively affects the quality of public library services.

Methodology

This study adopted descriptive research design targeting farmers as the core population. Eighty eight (88) farmers from the eight (8) wards in Dass Local Government were sampled for this study making a total of eleven (11) farmers from each ward using purposive sampling technique in selecting the sample. Therefore, a snowballing approach was used in reaching the farmers to fill the questionnaire. The data obtained were organized, analyzed, tabulated and interpreted using Statistical Package for Social Science (IBM-SPSS) version 16.0.

Results

Table 1: Demographic Distribution of Respondents (N = 88)

Demographic Variable	Category	Frequency	Percentage
Age	20–30	7	7.9%
	31–40	16	18.2%
	41–50	16	18.2%
	51–60	38	43.2%
	61 and above	11	12.5%
	Total	88	100%
Gender	Male	34	38.6%
	Female	54	61.4%
	Total	88	100%
Educational Qualification	None	33	37.5%
	Primary	18	20.5%
	Secondary	12	13.6%
	Diploma	10	11.4%
	B.Sc.	15	17.0%
	Total	88	100%
	Nature of Farm	Livestock	7
Crop		34	38.6%
Fishery		2	2.3%
Poultry		6	6.8%
Vegetables		38	43.2%
Rabbits		1	1.1%
Total		88	100%

Table 1 showed that majority of the farmers are female with 54(61.4%), while the male are 34(38.6%) of the total population. The 33(37.5%) of respondents in this study have no formal education, while the other respondents are holders of primary school certificate with 18(20.4), SSCE with 12(13.6%), Diploma with 10(11.3%), BSc holder with 15(17.0). From the total population, majority of the farmers have vegetable farm with 38(43.1) followed by crop farm with 32(38.6), livestock with 7(7.9), poultry with 6(6.8), fishery with 2(2.3) and rabbits farm. The age of farmers in this study showed that people at the age of 51-60 are the majority of farmers with 38(43.1) followed by 41-50 and 21-30 each with 16(18.1), 61 and above with 11(12.5) and 21-30 with 7(7.9) respectively. The study implies that majority of the sampled farmers in Dass Local Government are female between the age of 51-60 years and their nature of farm is majorly on vegetables and crops.

Table 2: Information Needs of Farmers (N=88)

Table with 6 columns: S/N, STATEMENTS, SA, A, D, SD. It lists six statements regarding farmers' information needs and their responses across five categories: SA, A, D, and SD.

Table 2 showed that 58(66%) of the farmers strongly agreed that they need information on agricultural input while 30(34%) agreed. 67(76%) strongly agreed on the need for economic information, 20(22.7) agreed and 1(1.1%) disagreed. The findings revealed that 58(65.9%) have the need for educational information while 30(34%) agreed. The finding also showed that 60(68.1%) need political information, 22(25%) agreed and 6(6.8%) strongly disagreed. 54(61.3%) strongly agreed on the need for environmental information, 30(34.0%) agreed and 4(4.5%) strongly disagreed. This implies that farmers need agricultural, economical, educational, political and environmental information.

Table 3: Information Sources of Farmers (N=88)

Table with 6 columns: S/N, STATEMENTS, SA, A, D, SD. It lists six statements regarding farmers' information sources and their responses across five categories: SA, A, D, and SD.

7	I get information from village square meetings.	22(25%)	58(66%)	6(6.8%)	2(2.3%)
8	I get information from watching documented films and slides.	21(23.8%)	50(56.8%)	12(13.6%)	7(8%)
9	I get information by consulting non-governmental organization	22(25%)	50(56.8%)	13(14.7%)	3(3.4%)

Table 3 showed that 30(34%) sources for information through the internet while 36(41%) agreed, 18(20.4%) disagreed and 4(4.5%) strongly disagreed. Using family and friends as a source of information, 60(68.1%) strongly agreed, 20(22.7%) agreed while 4(4.5%) disagreed and 2(2.3%) strongly disagreed. The finding also showed that 22(25%) strongly agreed to the use of newspaper and magazines, 58(66%) agreed while 8(9.1%) disagreed. 40(45.5%) listen to programs on radio, television and other media while 40(45.5%) agreed and 8(9.1%) disagreed. 23(26.1%) strongly agreed to the use of public library, 10(11.4%) agreed while 42(47.7%) disagreed and 13(14.7%) strongly disagreed. On farmers union/cooperative and other experienced farmers as a source of information, 40(45.5%) strongly agreed, 42(47.7%) agreed while 2(2.3) disagreed and 2(2.3%) strongly disagreed. 22(25%) strongly agreed to village square meetings as an information source while 58(66%) agreed, 6(6.8%) disagreed and 2(2.3) strongly disagreed. The finding also showed that 21(23.8%) strongly agreed to watching of documented films/slides as an information source while 50(56.8%) agreed, 12(13.6) disagreed and 7(8%) strongly disagreed. 22(25%) strongly agreed on consulting non-governmental organizations for information while 50(56.8%) agreed, 13(14.8%) disagreed and 3(3.4%) strongly disagreed. The findings of the study indicate that majority of the farmers' sampled source for information from family, friends, other experiences farmers and farmers union.

Table 4: Challenges faced by Farmers in using Public Library to get Information (N=88)

S/N	STATEMENTS	SA	A	D	SD
1	Foreign Language barrier	32(36.4%)	38(43.1%)	13(14.8%)	5(5.7%)
2	Lack of awareness	34(38.6%)	44(50%)	7(7.9%)	3(3.4%)
3	Long distance to the library	37(42%)	38(43.2%)	9(10.2%)	4(4.6%)
4	Lack of relevant materials in the library	35(39.8%)	38(43.2%)	12(13.6%)	4(4.6%)
5	Inadequate numbers of personnel to consult	32(36.4%)	48(54.6%)	4(4.6%)	4(4.6%)
6	Limited time for accessing information	27(30.7%)	38(43.2%)	15(17.1%)	8(9.1%)

Table 4 revealed that 32(36.4%) strongly agreed to language barrier as a challenge faced by farmers in using Bauchi State Public Library as a source of information, while 38(43.1%) agreed, 13(14.8%) disagreed and 5(5.7%) strongly disagreed. The finding also showed that 34(38.6%) strongly agreed to lack of awareness as a problem, while 44(50%) agreed, 7(7.9%) disagreed and 3(3.4%) strongly disagreed. About long distance to the library, 37(42%) strongly agreed, 38(43.2%) agreed, 9(10.2%) disagreed and 4(4.6%) strongly disagreed. 35(39.8%) strongly agreed to lack of relevant materials in the library, 38(43.2%) agreed while 12(13.6%) disagreed and 4(4.6%) strongly disagreed. On the problem of inadequate personnel to consult, 32(36.4%) strongly agreed while 48(54.6%) agreed, 4(4.6%) disagreed and 4(4.6%) strongly disagreed. The finding also revealed that 27(30.7%) strongly agreed on the problem of limited time for accessing

information, 38(43.2%) agreed while 15(17.1%) disagreed and 8(9.1%) strongly disagreed. Therefore, findings of the study suggest that majority of the farmers are faced with the problem of language barriers, lack of awareness, long distance to the library, inadequate personnel to consult and limited time for accessing information.

Discussion of Findings

In response to objective one, repositioning public library identify the information needs of farmers in Dass Local Government, Bauchi state. The findings of the study revealed that all the respondents have the need for agricultural information (agricultural input, processing methods, land preparation, agricultural equipments etc.) and educational information (agricultural training/workshop, children's education and the use of library). It also showed that majority needs economic information, political information, health information and environmental information. The findings corroborate the findings of Akeweta, Tata and Nandi (2018) and Benard, Dulle and Ngalapa (2018).

On the second objective, reposition public library to ascertain sources of information used by farmers in Dass Local government, Bauchi state. The findings of the study showed that more than half of the respondents prefer getting information from family and friends. However, this finding disagrees with the findings of Harande (2019) and agreed with the findings of Emmanuel (2022). Therefore it can be deduced from the findings that the source of information used by farmers can be affected by the level of development in the country. The findings also showed that few of the respondents perceived the public library as a source of information while majority does not. This finding supports the findings of Soylyu et al (2016). The rate at which the public library is used as a source can be as a result of awareness. Internet is not really perceived as a source of information but it is highly used compared to the library.

Regarding the responses to the third objective, repositioning public library to identify the challenges encountered by Bauchi State Public Library towards the provision of information to farmers in Dass Local Government, Bauchi state. The findings of the study showed that inadequate personnel to consult and lack of awareness is the most problem faced by farmers. Language barrier is a problem that came as a result of farmers' illiteracy, they are unable to comprehend foreign language easily and most books stocked in the library are written in English language. Idiegbeyan-Ose et al (2018) agreed with the above narrative. Other problems are long distance to the library, lack of relevant materials in the library and limited time for accessing information.

Conclusion and Recommendations

This study examined the repositioning public library to meet the information needs of farmers in Dass LGA. Despite the roles of public library in providing information to all and sundry, public library in Dass, Bauchi has not been able to meet the information needs of the farmers in the community it serves. Established from the findings of the study, it is clear that farmers are dissatisfied with the information materials and services available in Bauchi State Public Library. This is as a result of the poor state of information resources available, inadequate awareness service rendered by the library, lack of translator service and poor stocking of agricultural information resources which makes it difficult for farmers to get informed by using the library. In other for the

library to meet the information needs of farmers, the following recommendations were made based on the findings of the study:

1. Bauchi state government should assist in the provision of quality information needs of farmers by allocating more funds to the public library so that it can meet up with the evolving resources in the field of agriculture.
2. There is the need for policy makers to address the issue of the attitude of library staff in determining different sources of information used by farmers in order to provide services and ensure that staff are trained and retrained on customer relationships.
3. Public library in Bauchi should be decentralised in order to meet up with different challenges in the 21st century. This will help farmers to choose the nearest library branch to consult and all branches should be well stocked with adequate information resources and services.
4. Finally, agricultural information should be provided online by the public library. This will require the library to create a website stocked with information so that farmers who have little time to visit the library will be informed by using the library through the internet at one corner of their rooms. This service should be provided in different languages such as Hausa, English, Jhar, etc.

References

- Aguolu, I. E. (2000). Agricultural libraries and the dissemination of agricultural information in Nigeria. *Annals of Library Science and Documentation*, 47 (3), 115-119.
- Aina, L. O. (2006, January). Information provision to farmers in Africa: The role of libraries and extension services. *In World Library and Information Congress: IFLA Proceedings*.
- Akeweta, J. N., Tata, L. A. & Nandi, J. A. (2018) information needs of farmers in Song Local Government Area, Adamawa State, Nigeria. *Journal of Agriculture, Food Security and Sustainable Environment*, Vol. 1(1). Retrieved from <https://oer.fukashere.edu.ng/wp-content/uploads/2020/11/329-Jimwae-et-al-2018.pdf>
- American Library Association (2016). Social role of the library matter. Available at: http://www.ala.org/research/libraries_matter/taxonomy/term/143. (Accessed on: January 12, 2026).
- Benard, R., Dulle, F., Ngalapa, H. (2014) Assessment of information needs of rice farmers in Tanzania; A case study of Kilombero District, Morogoro. *Library Philosophy and Practice*, Vol. 2(4), p. 25-35. Retrieved from <https://scholarworks.sjsu.edu/libphilprac/1071/>
- Bhanu, M., & Dhanyasree, V. K. (2025). Promoting community engagement through public libraries: Initiatives of the Kerala State Library Council. *Journal of the Australian Library and Information Association*, 74(2), 199–219. <https://doi.org/10.1080/24750158.2025.2469376>

- Dent, V. F. (2006). *Modelling the rural community library: Characteristics of the Kitengesa Library in rural Uganda*. *New Library World*. (Note: While your original citation lists Dent et al. 2014, the widely cited work on rural community libraries by Dent appears in earlier literature on the Kitengesa Community Library.)
- Dent, V. F. (2012). Community libraries as agents for development and social change in Africa. *Library Trends*, 61(1), 55–73.
- Emmanuel, H. (2022). Information needs and information seeking behavior of rural farmers in Okpokwu Local Government Area of Benue State of Nigeria. *International Journal of Research and Innovation in Social Science (IJRISS)*, 4(5), 2454-6186
- Harande, Y. I. (2019). Information services for rural community development in Nigeria. *Library Philosophy and Practice*. *Library Philosophy and Practice*. (e-journal). Retrieved from <http://digitalcommons.edu/libphilprac/271> on 15 January, 2026.
- Idiegbeyan-Ose, J., Owolabi, A., Segun-Adeniran, C., Aregbesola, A., Owolabi S., & Eyiolorunshe T. (2018): Information provision by public library to agricultural extension agents in a developing country, *Public Library Quarterly*, 38, 103-115. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01616846.2018.1555412>
- Idris, Y. T. (2017). "Information needs, sources and information seeking behavior of women artisans in Offa Metropolis". *Library Philosophy and Practice* (e-journal). 1201
- IFLA/UNESCO *Public Library Manifesto* 1994. [Online] Available: <http://www.ifla.org/publication/iflaunesco-public-library-manifesto-1994>
- Jimma, W. (2018) The role of library and information services for rural development: The case of Ethiopia. *International Journal of Applied Research and Studies (iJARS)*, 3(2), 744-754. Retrieved from https://www.academia.edu/6303992/The_Role_of_Library_and_Information_Services_for_Rural_Development_The_Case_of_Ethiopia.
- John, O., Wakilu, O., & Olateju, A. (2018). Agricultural information needs of farmers in Lagos State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Agricultural Science Research*, 2(4), 116-123.
- Mojapelo, S. M. (2018). Challenges faced by libraries in a democratic South Africa: A case of three community libraries in Limpopo Province. *Information Development*, 34(4), 408–421.
- Momodu, M. O. (2002) Information needs and information seeking behavior of rural dwellers in Nigeria: A case study of Ekpoma in Esan West Local Government Area of Edo, Nigeria. *Library Review*, 51(8); 406-410
- Oluwaseunfunmi, O. A. (2020). Public libraries in Nigeria: resources and services for young adults. *International Journal of Library and Information Science Studies*, 1(2):1-13.

- Salman, A., Mostert, J., & Mugwisi, T. (2017) Access to and use of public library services in Nigeria. *South African Journal of Libraries and Information Science*, 83(1). Retrieved from <https://sajlis.journals.ac.za/pub/article/view/1639>
- Sobalaje, A. J., Gariba, A. O., & Adepoju, C. A. (2023). Role of libraries as sources for information by farmers in Ogbomoso, Oyo, Nigeria. *European-American Journal*, 9(7). Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.37745/ijliss.15/vol9n71125>
- Soylu, D., Cevher, N., Schirone, M., & Medeni, T. (2016). A comparative study of information-seeking behavior and digital information needs of farmers in Turkey and Sweden. *International Journal of e-business and e-government Studies*, 8(2), 2146-0744.
- Tarvinda, H. S. (2012). The future public library services in ICT with special reference to India. *Journal of Radix International Educational and Research Consortium*, 1(2), 30-41
- Tinuoye, O., Omeluzor, U., & Emeka-Ukwu, U. (2015) Rejuvenating public library services in Delta State for national development. *Open Access Library Journal*, 2(11); 1-9.
- Umoh, E., Habib, Z., & Yusuf, A. (2018). Role of public library in community development in Kano State. *International Journal of Operational Research in Management, Social Sciences & Education*, 4(1); 74-85